

Synthesis and characterization of manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II) complexes of a tellurium containing tetraazamacrocyclic : A photoelectron spectroscopic study

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Abstract : Some tellurium containing tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of the type RR^1TeL^1 , RR^1TeL^2 , RR^1TeL^3 and RR^1TeL^4 (where $R = R^1 = CH_3$ and $R = R^1 = C_6H_5CH_2$) have been prepared via template condensation of 1,2-diaminoethane or 1,3-diaminopropane with RR^1TeX_2 and metal salts. Elemental analysis, molar conductivity, PMR, IR, magnetic susceptibility measurements and X-ray photoelectron spectra have characterized the compounds. An octahedral geometry has been assigned for all these compounds.

Keywords : Tetraazamacrocyclic, photo-electron spectroscopy, bivalent metal ions, synthesis.

Recently Beer *et al.*¹ have described the synthesis of several polyazamacrocyclic complexes which incorporate both 'hard' and 'soft' metal ions and contain multiple metallocene redox active groups. Interest in macrocycle which contain 'hard' and 'soft' donor atoms to complex both 'hard' and 'soft' metal cations derives from their intrinsic potential for (i) modulation of the redox properties of a complexed 'soft' transition metal cation upon co-complexation of a 'hard' cation, (ii) allosteric effects and (iii) bimetallic activation and catalysis².

Although a few examples of polyazamacrocyclics containing 'soft' sulfur³ or phosphorous⁴ and 'hard' nitrogen donor atoms are known. Recently Singh *et al.*^{5,6} have been reported tellurium and selenium containing tetraazamacrocyclic.

In addition, the greater σ -donating ability of Te would facilitate the complexation of a variety of metal ions. Recently there have been extensive studies on the synthesis and ligating behavior of macrocyclic Schiff base containing phenol, pyridine, pyrrole, furan and thiophene units⁷. In recent years, the coordination behavior of organometallic compounds containing potentially bidentate ligand has been the subject of extensive studies⁸⁻¹¹.

In continuation of our work on tellurium, we report herein the synthesis and coordination chemistry of a novel 10-12 membered tellurium containing tetraazamacrocyclic (Te_2N_4 system) with more donor atoms.

Results and discussion

A new series of tellurium macrocycle was easily isolated via simple condensation of RR^1TeX_2 and 1,2-diaminoethane or 1,3-diaminopropane with transition metal ions template or high dilution reaction (Scheme 1). All the compounds were air-stable, had high melting points and soluble in DMSO, DMF, acetone etc. Elemental analyses were within $\pm 0.5\%$ for C, H, N and Te and molar conductance values in DMSO lied in the range 12-15 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, suggesting the compounds to be non-electrolyte¹³. However, we could not grow any single crystals suitable for X-ray crystallography studies. The IR spectra of all complexes did not show bands characteristics of free amine groups. Instead, the entire complexes exhibit a single sharp absorption band in the 3260-3320 cm^{-1} regions ascribed to $\nu(N-H)$ stretching vibration¹⁴. The above information's strongly suggest that the proposed ligand framework is formed. This has been further corroborated by the appearance of a sharp band in the 390-440 cm^{-1} region, which may reasonably be assigned to $\nu(M-N)$ ¹⁵. Bands observed in all complexes in the region 1160-1200 cm^{-1} may reasonably, be assigned to $\nu(C-N)$ stretching vibrations¹⁵. Bands observed in the regions 270-300 cm^{-1} in the chloro complexes are assignable to $\nu(M-Cl)$ ¹⁶. A band in the region 420-410 cm^{-1} present in the spectra of all complexes is assignable to $\nu(Te-N)$ vibration¹⁷. All the complexes showed bands in the region 560-540 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(Te-C)$ vibrations¹⁷.

Scheme 1

Manganese(II) complexes : The Mn^{II} complexes show magnetic moments corresponding to five unpaired electrons (5.96–6.01 B.M.) at room temperature, close to the spin only value of 5.92 B.M.

Electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes display weak absorption band at 17908–18210 (ν_1) ($\epsilon = 38\text{--}44 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 24986–25000 (ν_2) ($\epsilon = 47\text{--}51 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 28884–29156 (ν_3) ($\epsilon = 59\text{--}62 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) characteristic of the octahedral geometry¹⁸. In these complexes these bands may be assigned to the transition : ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^6A_{1g} ({}^4G) (10B + 5C)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g ({}^4D) (17B + 5C)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4P) (7B + 7C)$, respectively.

Cobalt(II) complexes : At room temperature the magnetic moment values of the cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.98–5.02 B.M. corresponding to three unpaired electrons. The electronic spectra of all the cobalt(II) complexes exhibit absorption in the region 8693–8827 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 53\text{--}57 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 14476–14541 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 68\text{--}73 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 18656–21055 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 91\text{--}97 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). These bands may be assigned to the following transitions : ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (\nu_2)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$, respectively. These transitions suggest an octahedral environment^{19–22} around the cobalt ion.

Nickel(II) complexes : At room temperature these complexes show magnetic moment in the range 2.94–2.98 B.M. These values correspond to a high spin configuration and show the presence of an octahedral environment²³ around the nickel(II) ion in the complexes.

The electronic spectra of the complexes display three absorption bands in the range 9997–10526 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon =$

36–42 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 16257–16642 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 66\text{--}73 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 24867–24876 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 121\text{--}127 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). These bands may be assigned to the three spin allowed transitions : ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ respectively, corresponding to an octahedral geometry^{18,19,21}.

Copper(II) complexes : The magnetic moment measurements of the Cu^{II} complexes at RT lie in the range 1.99–2.01 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron. Electronic spectra of copper complexes display bands in the range 10219–10348 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 62\text{--}65 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_3), 14448–14640 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 76\text{--}81 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_2) and 20161–20234 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 127\text{--}132 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_3). These bands may be considered to the following three spin allowed transitions¹⁹ : ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} (d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}) (\nu_1)$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g} (d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g (d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{zy}, d_{yz}) (\nu_3)$.

The PMR spectra of all tellurium containing macrocyclic complexes show no signal corresponding to secondary amino protons indicating that the proposed macrocyclic skeleton has been formed during the condensation reaction. A multiplet appearance at 2.02–2.35 ppm^{24,25} for the complex L^1 and L^3 may be assigned to the middle methylene protons- CH_2 (4H) of the proton chain.

The photoelectron peaks binding energies data for Te $3d_{3/2,5/2}$ and N 1s for $[RR^1TeX_2]$ and $[MLCl_2]$ (where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$; $L = L^1, L^2, L^3, L^4$) are listed in Table 1. It may be seen that the binding energy of Te $3d_{3/2,5/2}$ photoelectron peaks have no change in all prepared $[MLCl_2]$ complexes than RR^1TeX_2 , whereas, M $2p_{3/2}$ ($M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$) photoelectron peaks binding energies have been decreased from their

Table 1. M $2p_{3/2}$ (M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}), Te $3d_{3/2,5/2}$ and N 1s binding energies (eV) in RR^ITeX₂ and their RR^ITeL compounds

Compd.	Color	Metal ion			N 1s N (coord.)
		M $2p_{3/2}$	Te $3d_{3/2}$	Te $3d_{5/2}$	
(CH ₃) ₂ TeI ₂	Brownish black	-	583.2	573.6	-
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O		642.2	-	-	-
[MnL ¹ Cl ₂]	Pale brown	640.25	583.2	573.6	402.2
[MnL ² Cl ₂]	Brown	640.25	583.2	573.6	402.4
[MnL ³ Cl ₂]	Light brown	640.25	583.2	573.6	402.2
[MnL ⁴ Cl ₂]	Reddish brown	640.25	583.2	573.6	402.4
CoCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O		781.2	-	-	-
[CoL ¹ Cl ₂]	Dark brown	779.25	583.2	573.6	402.6
[CoL ² Cl ₂]	Pink	779.25	583.2	573.6	402.6
[CoL ³ Cl ₂]	Pinkish brown	779.25	583.2	573.6	402.8
[CoL ⁴ Cl ₂]	Brown	779.25	583.2	573.6	402.6
NiCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O		857.2	-	-	-
[NiL ¹ Cl ₂]	Light green	855.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
[NiL ² Cl ₂]	Shiny blue	855.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
[NiL ³ Cl ₂]	Dark blue	855.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
[NiL ⁴ Cl ₂]	Blackish blue	855.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
CuCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O		933.2	-	-	-
[CuL ¹ Cl ₂]	Navy blue	931.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
[CuL ² Cl ₂]	Light blue	931.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
[CuL ³ Cl ₂]	Blue	931.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
[CuL ⁴ Cl ₂]	Dark blue	931.2	583.2	573.6	402.6
ZnCl ₂	White	89.2	-	-	-
[ZnL ¹ Cl ₂]	Off white	87.25	583.2	573.6	402.8
[ZnL ² Cl ₂]	Off white	87.25	583.2	573.6	402.6
[ZnL ³ Cl ₂]	Off white	87.25	583.2	573.6	402.6
[ZnL ⁴ Cl ₂]	Off white	87.25	583.2	573.6	402.6

salts i.e. MnCl₂·4H₂O, CoCl₂·4H₂O, NiCl₂·4H₂O, CuCl₂·4H₂O and ZnCl₂ in these prepared [MLCl₂] complexes. Furthermore, N 1s photoelectron peak in each prepared [MLCl₂] complexes have shown a single symmetrical and with high positive chemical shifts. These XPS data and their observations conclude that tellurium metal ion is not coordinated with metal ion i.e. Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} but all four nitrogen atoms are coordinated to metal ion Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} ^{26,31}. On the basis of the above physico-chemical studies, a tentative structure may be proposed (Scheme 1).

Experimental

The (CH₃)₂TeI₂ ²⁷, (C₆H₅CH₂)TeI₂ ¹⁷, were prepared by reported procedures. Air sensitive reactions were carried out under an inert atmosphere. The metal salts were purchased from E. Merck, Fluka and B.D.H. used as

received. The chemicals 1,3-diaminopropane, 1,2-diaminoethane (Sisco) was reagent grade and was distilled prior to use.

Synthesis of 10-membered tellurium tetraazamacrocyclic (TeN₄M system) : A mixture of RR^ITeX₂ (2 mmol) and 1,2-diaminopropane (2 mmol) in methanol (~75 cm³) was stirred with gentle heating for about 2 h. This was followed by the addition of a methanolic solution of metal salts (1 mmol) and the resulting mixture was refluxed for about 3 h, resulting in the formation of solid product obtained by rotary evaporation, which were filtered, washed with pet-ether and vacuum-dried.

Synthesis of 12-membered tellurium tetraazamacrocyclic (TeN₄M system) : These compounds were prepared by the same procedure given above but instead of 1,2-diaminoethane; here 1,3-diaminopropane (2 mmol) was added.

Characterization of the complexes: The microanalytical laboratory obtained from CDRI, Lucknow, India, made elemental analyses. Conductance measurements were obtained in DMSO at room temperature using a Digisum Electronic Conductivity Bridge. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. The IR spectra ($4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded as CsI disc on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra in DMSO- d_6 using a Bruker AC 200E spectrometer with Me_4Si as an internal standard were obtained from I.I.T. Kanpur, India. Metals and chloride were determined volumetrically²⁸ and gravimetrically²⁹ respectively. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by the Faraday method using Cahn Magnetic Susceptibility System. $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ was used as a standard for calibration³⁰. The X-ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on a VG Scientific ESCA-3MK II electron spectrometer. The Mg $K\alpha$ X-ray line (1253.6 eV) was used for photo-excitation. The Cu $2p_{3/2}$ (BE = 932.8 ± 0.2) and Au $4f_{7/2}$ (BE = 83.8 ± 0.1) lines were used to calibrate the instrument and Ag $3d_{5/2}$ (BE = 368.2) was used for cross checking³¹. All the spectra were recorded using the same spectrometer parameters of 50 eV pass energy and 4 mm slit width. The reduced full width at half maximum (FWHM) at the Au $4f_{7/2}$ (BE = 83.2 eV) level under these conditions was 1.2 eV.

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